

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Some Pyrazolyl Schiff Bases

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Thirty-six Schiff bases were prepared by condensing pyrazolyl-phenyl ketone with *o*-, *m*-, *p*-substituted aryl amines. Fungitoxicity of these compounds was studied against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*. 32 compounds showed significant fungicidal activity against *P. oryzae* and 19 compounds showed significant fungicidal activity against *H. oryzae*.

IN view of the significant fungicidal activity¹ exhibited by the pyrazolyl-phenyl ketone, this study of the fungitoxicity of the Schiff bases derived from the said ketone was taken up. Thus the present investigation forms a part of our programme of studies on heterocyclic fungicides²⁻⁵. Condensation of the ethanolic solution of the phenyl ketone with aromatic amino compound affords the Schiff's base. The formation of the Schiff's base has been proved from the following observations :

- (1) failure to react with characteristic carbonyl group reagent,
- (2) positive test with ethanolic FeCl₃ and solubility in aqueous alkali indicating the presence of a free

- (3) IR : 1615 cm⁻¹ (ring $\begin{array}{c} \diagdown \\ \text{C}=\text{O} \\ \diagup \end{array}$). The IR bend at 1680 cm⁻¹ (exocyclic $\begin{array}{c} \diagdown \\ \text{C}=\text{O} \\ \diagup \end{array}$) in phenyl-ketone disappears.

Thirty-six Schiff's bases thus prepared during the present investigation were screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *P. oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *H. oryzae* by the standard method⁶ using spore germination test at various concentrations. The fungicidal activities of the compounds at 1000 ppm concentration are given in Table I. Thirty-two compounds exhibited encouraging fungicidal activity against *P. oryzae*, except the four compounds (Sl. No. 6, 10, 24, 35). The activity was found to be maximum with the compound Sl. No. 29 which inhibited 70 and 98% of *P. oryzae* spore germination at 250 and 1000 ppm concentration respectively. Nineteen compounds (Sl. No. 1, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 13, 15, 17, 18, 19, 20, 24,

25, 28, 29, 30, 36) exhibited promising activity against *H. oryzae* while the remaining seventeen compounds did not show significant activity. It was observed that the highest activity was found in case of compound Sl. No. 19 which inhibited 65 and 84% of *H. oryzae* spore germination at 250 and 1000 ppm concentration respectively. The fungicidal activities of the compounds thus studied were compared with some standard fungicides like *o*-ethyl-S, S-diphenyl phosphorodithioate (Hinosan 50%) EC, Difolatan 50% WP, Derosal 60% WP which inhibited 95, 98, 87% of spore germination of *P. oryzae* respectively at 1000 ppm concentration. We further noticed that the fungicidal activity of the five compounds (Sl. No. 1, 5, 19, 26 and 29) are good in comparison with the standard fungicides, hence these can be used as commercial fungicides.

Experimental

Pyrazolyl-phenyl ketone :

It was prepared by us following the method reported earlier¹.

Schiff base : (Table I)

Pyrazolyl-phenyl ketone (0.01 mole) and substituted amine (0.01 mole) were taken in ethanol (20 ml) and refluxed for 2 hr on a water bath, cooled. Excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and residue allowed to stand overnight. Since no solid was separated out, it was treated with water. The compound thus separated was filtered and crystallized from ethanol. The compound gave colouration with ethanolic FeCl₃ and was soluble in 10% NaOH solution. The m.p. and analytical data of the compounds thus prepared are listed in Table I.

TABLE I—SCHIFF'S BASES DERIVED FROM PYRAZOLYLPHENYL KETONE

X = C₆H₅ (1-18), X = H (19-36)

Sl. No.	Amino compounds used "N-Y"	M.P. (°C)	% Found (Calc.)			% inhibition at 1000 ppm conc.	
			C	H	N	<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	Aniline	268	78.12	4.93	11.41	88	62
2.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	248	(78.47)	(5.72)	(11.44)	78	58
3.	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	202	71.23	4.37	10.02	70	69
4.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	234	(71.82)	(4.98)	(10.47)	66	52
5.	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	177	71.91	4.13	10.34	90	73
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	214	(71.82)	(4.98)	(10.47)	51	66
7.	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	170	71.05	4.38	10.11	68	43
8.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	201	(71.82)	(4.98)	(10.47)	73	70
9.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	250	70.24	4.87	13.07	79	62
10.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	248	(69.9)	(4.85)	(13.59)	52	63
11.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	244	69.71	4.39	13.17	82	40
12.	<i>m</i> -Anisidine	238	(69.9)	(4.85)	(13.59)	69	51
13.	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	224	69.63	4.35	13.18	72	60
14.	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	210	(69.9)	(4.85)	(13.59)	68	47
15.	Anthranilic acid	250	78.39	5.92	10.98	71	69
16.	α -Naphthylamine	196	(78.74)	(6.03)	(11.02)	81	53
17.	β -Naphthylamine	280	78.62	6.14	10.74	60	70
18.	2-Amino-benzothiazole	255	(78.74)	(6.03)	(11.02)	60	67
19.	Aniline	234	78.19	5.76	11.01	94	84
20.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	222	(78.74)	(6.03)	(11.02)	73	75
21.	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	218	75.17	5.32	10.43	67	54
22.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	206	(75.56)	(5.79)	(10.57)	64	43
23.	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	208	75.29	5.61	10.39	75	38
24.	<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	232	(75.56)	(5.79)	(10.57)	50	60
25.	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	223	75.41	5.17	10.24	60	62
26.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	204	(75.56)	(5.79)	(10.57)	92	55
27.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	220	72.48	4.96	10.08	69	64
28.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	226	(72.99)	(5.1)	(10.21)	70	67
29.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	236	80.18	5.09	10.37	98	67
			(80.57)	(5.51)	(10.07)		
			79.88	5.43	10.52		
			(80.57)	(5.51)	(10.07)		
			70.19	4.31	13.04		
			(70.75)	(4.71)	(13.2)		
			74.06	5.42	14.09		
			(74.22)	(5.84)	(14.43)		
			86.03	4.48	12.62		
			(66.39)	(4.91)	(12.90)		
			66.17	4.39	13.01		
			(66.39)	(4.91)	(12.90)		
			66.29	4.58	12.81		
			(66.39)	(4.91)	(12.90)		
			64.46	4.69	16.19		
			(64.28)	(4.76)	(16.66)		
			64.05	4.32	16.46		
			(64.28)	(4.76)	(16.66)		
			64.12	4.52	16.37		
			(64.28)	(4.76)	(16.66)		
			74.35	6.07	10.17		
			(74.75)	(6.22)	(13.77)		
			74.27	6.14	10.08		
			(74.75)	(6.22)	(13.77)		
			74.19	5.98	10.23		
			(74.75)	(6.22)	(13.77)		
			70.96	5.37	12.89		
			(71.02)	(5.91)	(13.08)		

(Table 1 Contd.)

Sl. No.	Amino compounds used "N—Y"	M.P. (°C)	% Found (Calc.)			% inhibition at 1000 ppm conc.	
			C	H	N	<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
30.	<i>m</i> -Anisidine	215	71.43 (71.02)	6.18 (5.91)	12.67 (13.08)	72	64
31.	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	212	71.26 (71.02)	5.98 (5.91)	12.93 (13.08)	83	47
32.	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	233	68.21 (68.05)	5.62 (5.07)	12.41 (12.53)	69	44
33.	Anthranilic acid	207	67.96 (68.05)	4.98 (5.07)	12.21 (12.53)	65	48
34.	α -Naphthylamine	200	77.17 (77.41)	5.32 (5.57)	12.09 (12.31)	75	54
35.	β -Naphthylamine	214	77.06 (77.41)	5.17 (5.57)	12.16 (12.31)	57	52
36.	2-Aminobenzothiazole	212	65.13 (65.51)	4.27 (4.59)	16.01 (16.09)	72	61

Yield of the compounds varied between 45-80%.

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